

The Use of “Kodrat” Digital Game Media to Improve Online Students’ Learning Motivation at Sekolah Indonesia Kota Kinabalu

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ABSTRACT: This research was motivated by the existence of Indonesian diaspora students in Sabah, Malaysia, who experienced difficulties in continuing their education to high school level in Indonesia. Currently, the only school available is Sekolah Indonesia Kota Kinabalu (SIKK), which has limited capacity and cannot accommodate many students each school year. As a solution, the existence of Long-Distance Integrated Senior High School (SMA TJJ) was initiated, but it still faces various problems, especially in conventional learning methods so that students' learning motivation is low. The aim of this research is to provide alternative game-based learning media to increase SMA TJJ students' learning motivation in learning Bahasa Indonesia. The game used in this research was named "KODRAT". The research method used is a qualitative method with instruments in the form of observation and interviews. The research results showed that the learning motivation of SMA TJJ students at the Sekolah Indonesia Kota Kinabalu (SIKK) increased after teachers implemented games-based learning. This increase in motivation can be seen from students' enthusiasm in participating in learning, active participation in each session, as well as a significant increase in language learning outcomes.

KEYWORDS: game-based learning media, learning motivation, online students

INTRODUCTION

SIKK is an Indonesian school abroad located in Sabah, Malaysia, serving nearly 20,000 Indonesian diaspora students across Sabah and Sarawak. However, only about 5 percent can be accommodated in the SIKK building. The rest of the students are spread across 143 Community Learning Centers (CLCs) scattered throughout Sabah and Sarawak. However, the education levels served by these CLCs are only elementary and junior high school levels. Subsequently, students who intend to continue to high school can apply and take the selection test to enter SIKK. Nevertheless, the quota for offline learning groups is quite limited due to the availability of classroom buildings at SIKK.

One of the policies made by SIKK as a solution to facilitate high school students who have not been accommodated is by opening online classes. This aligns with Friedrich's opinion (in Lafitef, et al., 2021: 75), which states that a policy is proposed by an individual, group, or government in a particular environment where there are obstacles and possibilities related to provisions to achieve the intended goals. This policy is named SMA TJJ (Integrated Distance Learning Senior High School). In 2024, according to data provided by the person in charge of SMA TJJ, there are about 262 students taking online classes to receive the same learning rights at SIKK.

On the other hand, the development of the information industry has successfully changed the world, especially after the Covid-19 pandemic era. The existence of the pandemic tested the progress of science and technology created by humans. Nowadays, many human activities can take place through the virtual world, including learning activities in the field of education.

Technology has also successfully fulfilled its essence of making human work easier, saving costs, making tasks more effective, and time-efficient. Thus, the role of technology in learning activities will connect all educational subjects (Latief, et al., 2021: 145).

Furthermore, according to Hakim (in Khrisna, 2022: 8), learning is a process of change in human personality, and this change is manifested in the form of increased quality and quantity of behavior such as skills, knowledge, attitudes, habits, understanding, abilities, thinking power, and other capabilities. Therefore, if in a learning process a person does not experience an increase in the quality and quantity of their abilities, it can be said that the person has not experienced the learning process or has failed in their learning process.

The policy of Sekolah Indonesia Kota Kinabalu (SIKK) in organizing SMA TJJ is not without challenges. According to the author's observations, there is still a lot of student boredom in SMA TJJ when participating in online learning. If linked to the above assumption, it can affect the educational process of the students.

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Learning boredom is usually influenced by several factors. One of the most influential is routine learning without variation over long periods without breaks. In addition, an unsupportive online learning environment, conflicts in the learning environment, or issues between students and teachers or peers are other factors (Khrisna, 2022: 8).

There are quite a few solutions from education experts to overcome this learning boredom, especially in the implementation of online learning such as SMA TJJ at SIKK. One alternative solution is the use of innovative digital learning media by teachers.

The use of digital learning media is becoming increasingly important, especially in the context of online education. This research tries to explore how various forms of digital learning media can increase student motivation in an online learning environment.

According to Bokarewa Katona, et al. (2023: 162), the use of interactive visual learning media used by teachers can increase student motivation. This is because during the learning process using visual media, educators are required to be able to understand what is being conveyed and try to make learning interesting for students so that students will be enthusiastic in participating in learning.

Apart from that, according to Safitri, D., et al. (2022: 191), digital game-based learning media has a positive effect on student learning motivation so that it is effective in increasing learning motivation. This is because digital game-based learning media is relevant to certain game maneuvers for learning that expect results, but in this model it also emphasizes other elements, such as metacognition and knowledge transfer for students so that in addition to the enjoyable learning experience students gain, understanding and knowledge of the material also need to be paid attention to.

Based on this, researchers developed an alternative game-based digital learning media to increase student motivation online in learning the Indonesian language. The digital game used in this study is named "KODRAT."

"KODRAT" is a digital edugame in the Slash Action genre, where students must complete missions based on learning objectives at the beginning of the game. This game is implemented in the "Folktales" or "Hikayat" material in the Indonesian language.

METHODS

This research is qualitative descriptive research. Its focuses on determining meaning, describing, clarifying and placing data in their respective contexts. This research usually describes data with words rather than numbers (Mahsun, 2007: 257).

In the qualitative descriptive research method, the collected data is not a collection of numbers, but comes from a collection of (1) interview scripts, from interview transcripts conducted by researchers with related sources. (2) Field notes, notes made by researchers when they go directly and observe the object being studied. (3) Personal documentation, by documenting findings in the field with photos or videos. (4) Official documents, in the form of official data regarding the object being studied (Meleong, 2005: 15).

The research location used by researchers was the Kota Kinabalu Indonesian School (SIKK), in Kota Kinabalu, Sabah, Malaysia. This is because TJJ SIKK SMA is based and has its office at the Kota Kinabalu Indonesian School (SIKK).

Data analysis used in this research uses the Miles and Huberman analysis model. Miles and Huberman stated that activities in qualitative data analysis are carried out interactively and continue continuously until completion, so that the data is saturated. Activities in data analysis, namely data collection, data condensation, data display, and drawing/verifying conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. General Overview of SMA TJJ SIKK

Program SMA TJJ at Sekolah Indonesia Kota Kinabalu (SIKK) was established to address the concerns of students and parents in continuing formal education for Indonesian students abroad, especially in Sabah, Malaysia. The SMA TJJ program combines synchronous and asynchronous distance learning while considering learning principles according to established standards without diminishing the essence of education.

The SMA TJJ program is based on three existing regulatory references:

- (1) Indonesian Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 119 of 2014 concerning the Implementation of Distance Education for Elementary and Secondary Education Levels.
- (2) Indonesian Minister of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology Decree No. 213/P/2021 regarding the Implementation of Distance Education for High Schools in Kota Kinabalu.
- (3) The Principal's Decree of SIKK on the division of teachers' duties.

According to the SOP Book of the SMA TJJ Program (SIKK, 2024: 3-7), the program has certain stipulations. These stipulations are divided into two categories: general provisions and specific provisions. The general provisions are as follows:

- (1) The SMA TJJ SIKK learning is carried out with the principle of quality learning to maximize students' potential.
- (2) The SMA TJJ SIKK learning uses two methods: (1) synchronous method and (2) asynchronous method.
- (3) During synchronous learning, teachers and students must prepare electronic media (HP/PC) and ensure the learning location has good internet access to support synchronous learning implementation.
- (4) The synchronous learning platforms that can be used are Zoom and/or Google Classroom.

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- (5) The asynchronous learning platforms that can be used are WhatsApp Groups, Telegram, Email, Google Forms, and/or other media.
- (6) The synchronous learning pattern is carried out following the class schedule.
- (7) The asynchronous learning pattern is carried out based on the agreement between teachers and students.

Furthermore, the specific provisions are divided into three segments: for teachers, for students, and for parents. Here are the explanations:

(1) For Teachers

- a. Teachers must prepare learning materials in the form of documents (Word, PPT, or others), audio, and/or video based on the lesson plans or modules created.
- b. Teachers must provide active WhatsApp numbers and emails.
- c. Teachers prepare the attendance list for students.
- d. Teachers must prepare assignments (knowledge and skills) to monitor learning activities and achievements.
- e. Teachers conduct synchronous learning according to the class schedule and times set by the SMA TJJ curriculum department.
- f. Teachers conduct synchronous learning at school except under certain conditions approved by the SIKK Principal.
- g. Teachers must communicate the rules during synchronous learning activities.
- h. Teachers are responsible for conditioning students during synchronous learning activities to ensure an active and conducive learning environment.
- i. Teachers conduct learning wearing the prescribed school uniform.
- j. Teachers provide motivation and encouragement to students during synchronous learning.
- k. Teachers must provide feedback or responses to assignments given.
- l. Teachers report learning activities and achievements to the class advisor, SMA TJJ curriculum department, and the principal.
- m. Teachers who are unable to attend synchronous learning must report to the deputy head of the SMA TJJ curriculum department.

(2) For Students

- a. Students can access synchronous learning materials and assignments from their respective locations.
- b. If students have internet network issues, they should report to the subject teacher or class advisor immediately.
- c. Students are expected to connect to the synchronous learning application according to the specified schedule.
- d. Students must create a learning application account with their real name and a clear profile photo.
- e. Students must fill out the attendance list.
- f. Students must activate their video during synchronous learning.
- g. Students must follow synchronous learning and adhere to the rules provided by the subject teacher in an orderly, enthusiastic, and proactive manner.
- h. Students must wear neat and proper clothing.
- i. Students must maintain courtesy and ethics during synchronous learning.
- j. Students are prohibited from lying down, eating, or engaging in other activities that may disrupt synchronous learning.
- k. Students who are unable to attend must report to the respective subject teacher.
- l. Synchronous learning is considered complete when closed by the subject teacher.
- m. Students who cannot adhere to the school's specified rules will be removed from synchronous learning and considered absent.
- n. If students cannot participate in synchronous learning for one consecutive month, they will receive a First Warning Letter (SP1), and a home visit scheme by the tutor/academic advisor (local CLC teacher) will be conducted. If the student remains absent for one week after SP1 is issued, they will receive a Second Warning Letter (SP2). If the student remains absent for one week after SP2 is issued, they will receive a Third Warning Letter and be considered to have withdrawn as a student of the Indonesian School of Kota Kinabalu.

(3) For Parents

- a. Parents of students must provide learning facilities that can support synchronous and asynchronous learning.
- b. Parents are expected to remind their children of the synchronous learning schedule.
- c. Parents are expected to remind and supervise the synchronous and asynchronous learning process.
- d. Parents are expected to remind and supervise students in completing and submitting synchronous learning assignments.
- e. Parents are expected to condition the learning environment so that the learning process can proceed well.
- f. Parents are expected to coordinate with the school if their child experiences difficulties in the synchronous learning process.
- g. Parents are expected to continue motivating their children in the implementation of synchronous and asynchronous learning.

2. The Use of “KODRAT” Digital Game Media

“KODRAT” is an digital edugame with the Slash Action Genre, where students must complete missions based on learning objectives at the start of the game. This game is implemented in the material "Folklore" or “Hikayat” in Indonesian.

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This game was created using the RPG Maker VX Ace application. This application is a development of the RPG Maker application. Developed by the Japanese corporation ASCII, RPG Maker (also known as RPG *Tsukūru*, or RPG ツクール; often romanized as RPG Tkool) is a series of programs for the creation of role-playing video games (RPGs) featuring story-driven aspects. Enterbrain and Gotcha Gotcha Games followed in the creators' footsteps. The Japanese name *Tsukūru* is a *pun* that combines the meaning of "make" or "create," *tsukuru* (作る), with the Japanese transcription of the English word "tool," *tsūru* (ツール).

Using a tool called RPG Maker, users can make their own role-playing video games. The majority of versions come with a battle editor, a basic scripting language for creating events, and a tileset-based map editor (pre-XP versions referred to tilesets as chipsets). The original prefabricated tile sets, characters, and events are included in all versions and can be utilized to create new games. One aspect of RPG Maker programs for PCs is the ability to add any additional visuals and create custom tilesets and characters.

Though primarily designed for generating role-playing video games, the engine may also be used to make games of other genres with minimum modifications, like adventure games (like *Yume Nikki*) or story-driven games like graphic novels.

December 15, 2011, was the release date of RPG Maker VX Ace in Japan; the West received it on March 15, 2012. Later on, it became accessible via Steam in addition to being physically available. The tileset issue was resolved in VX Ace, an updated version of VX. The battle backgrounds have been brought back and are divided by upper and lower sections. It is now possible for spells, talents, and items to have their own damage and recovery algorithms, while there is also a fast calculating approach that is reminiscent of previous RPG Makers. For the VX Ace, the VX RTP was revamped, and a new soundtrack with better techno-pop songs was added. Alongside VX Ace, Enterbrain released a ton of DLC Resource Packages that were accessible via Steam as well.

The researchers developed this application over approximately three months with the following objectives for students:

- (1) Facilitate students in independently understanding the basic concepts of learning materials.
- (2) Achieve an increase in cognitive competence of the learning material.
- (3) Provide alternative new learning strategies so that students can better understand the material taught.
- (4) Observe positive behavioral/motivational changes in students during learning.

The Learning Outcomes achieved in the game "KODRAT" are that students can understand the definition, characteristics, and structure of *hikayat* (folktales) and can independently retell and respond to the content.

The description of the learning media is in the form of a PC game application with a Slash Action genre. The main character is the student themselves. The student represents themselves as the character Rama, who is searching for his wife, Sinta. In this world, Rama will meet other characters who support the core story. However, during his adventure, he will encounter a character named Pak Panji, who acts as a teacher providing materials and guidance throughout the journey. The game concludes when Rama finds his wife in the story.

The tools and materials needed for this game are a laptop or PC and the "KODRAT" edugame application, which has been distributed to students. However, during the learning process, teachers can also represent students in playing and adventuring as Rama. The teacher's gameplay screenshots can be shared through the screen-sharing feature in Zoom meetings.

3. The Use of Digital Game Media "KODRAT" in Bahasa Indonesia Learning to Increase Student Motivation in the SMA TJJ Program

The research results show that online high school students' learning motivation at SIKK increased after teachers implemented “KODRAT” games-based learning. This increase in motivation can be seen from students' enthusiasm in participating in learning, active participation in each session, as well as a significant increase in language learning outcomes.

Of the 72 online students who took part in the questionnaire, there were 95,8 percent of students who admitted to being motivated about “KODRAT” learning. Only 2,8 percent said they were doubtful and only 1,3 percent said they didn't like “KODRAT” learning.

As many as 59,7 percent admitted to "very understand" of the basic concepts of “Hikayat” in online Indonesian language learning. Then, there were 36,1 percent who said they were "starting to understand" the basic concepts of “Hikayat”. And only 4,1 percent still "don't understand" the basic concept of “Hikayat” using “KODRAT”.

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As many as 16,7 students thought that “KODRAT” learning was "a new thing" for them, while 83,3 percent thought that “KODRAT” learning made them “enthusiastic” about learning online.

CONCLUSION

Digital learning media, including interactive multimedia, digital games, smart books, virtual media, and web-based platforms, have been shown to significantly enhance student motivation in online learning environments. These tools make learning more engaging, interactive, and enjoyable, thereby fostering a more effective and motivating educational experience.

The research results showed that the learning motivation of SMA TJJ at Sekolah Indonesia Kota Kinabalu (SIKK) increased after teachers implemented “KODRAT” digital games-based learning. This increase in motivation can be seen from students' enthusiasm in participating in learning, active participation in each session, as well as a significant increase in language learning outcomes.

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